

Transmitting a Distance Training Model to the Community in the Upper Northeastern Region

Teerawach Khamkorn, Laongtip Mathurasa, Savittree Rochanasmita Arnold, and Witthaya Mekhum

Abstract—The objective of this research seeks to transmit a distance training model to the community in the upper northeastern region. The group sampling consists of 60 community leaders in the municipality of sub-district Kumphawapi, Kumphawapi District, Udonthani Province. The research tools rely on the following instruments, they are : 1) the achievement test of community leaders' training and 2) the satisfaction questionnaires of community leaders. The statistics used in data analysis takes the statistical mean, percentage, standard deviation, and statistical T-test. The resulted findings reveal : 1) the efficiency of the distance training developed by the researcher for the community leaders joining in the training received the average score between in-training and post-training period higher than the setup criterion, 2) the two groups of participants in the training achieved higher knowledge than their pre-training state, 3) the comparison of the achievements between the two group presented no different results, 4) the community leaders obtained the high-to-highest satisfaction.

Keywords—Distance Training, Management, Technology, Transmitting.

I. INTRODUCTION

FOR the national development to achieve the potential increase and firm standing, all parties concerned must realize the necessity of “human quality” development. Importantly, the participation from all sectors in the society can strive towards the “human-centered development” in which the balanced development will lead to the sustainable development and well-being of the people in Thailand [4]. One way towards “human” development is to rely on training, a process which consumes much less time than general classroom instructions. Training opens an education opportunity to individuals through practice under the guidance of learned experts [3]. Training brings forth a systematic change and development of skills and attitude through the learning experience [1]. Although, training is considered a necessity for development of skills, knowledge and competency of individuals involved, it faces with many problems and obstacles. In managing training, a distance of training locations and training course design irrelevant to the needs of participants become problematic as well as insufficient numbers of facilitators and staff and inadequate funding for

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training [6]. From these problems and obstacles associated with training, the researcher has built a distance training model for the community leaders in the upper northeastern region in order to further transmit this knowledge region wide. This effort is expected to serve as a guide for sustainable community development.

II. METHODOLOGY

The objective of this research intends to transmit the distance training model to the community in the upper northeastern region. The researcher wrote to the mayor of the municipality of sub-district Kumphawapi, Kumphawapi District, Udonthani Province, asking for his cooperation in applying the researcher's distance training model to the community leaders in the municipality of sub-district Kumphawapi.

Fig. 1 The mayor of the municipality of sub-district Kumphawapi

The group sampling used in this research is the community leaders in the municipality of sub-district district Kumphawapi, Kumphawapi District, Udonthani Province. They have registered and received the training in the number of 60 people. They have passed the tests of basic knowledge. The first group, 30 community leaders, received the training in the training room of the Udonthani Rajabhat University. The second group did so in the training room on the second floor of the Municipal Office of sub-district Kumphawapi, Kumphawapi District, Udonthani Province.

Fig. 2 The Municipal Office of sub-district Kumphawapi

Fig. 3 The training room of the municipality of sub-district Kumphawapi

The research tools in this endeavor are : 1) the achievement tests of community leaders' training in the analysis of the test of confidence interval according to 0.92, 2) the satisfaction questionnaires of community leaders, the type of choices with the rating scales of Likert's formula-most, very, moderate, low least-corresponding to the respective numerical scales of 5,4,3,2,1. Each questionnaire has 20 questions which have been examined by a panel of 5 experts and expressed in the Index of Item Objective Congruence (IOC) with the value between 0.80-1.00.

The steps in implementing the distance training model for the community leaders runs along the following phases.

1. To study the principle, policy and the goal of the municipality of sub-district Kumphawapi to determine the strategy of distance training for the community leaders.

2. To provide the personnel preparedness through the meeting to determine the role and duty of each individual. While the lecturer was speaking in the training room of Udonthani Rajabhat University, he sent the signal through the system of distance learning to the second group in the training room of the municipality of sub-district Kumphawapi.

3. Preparing the tools and equipment has to do with computers, stereo equipment, speakers, webcam, projectors and the internet network; all of which are the available resources in the municipality of sub-district Kumphawapi. Definitely, they can be adapted and deployed to work in the distance training situation.

4. As for the preparation for the training course and its contents, the course design is assigned under the title "Way of life in the sufficiency economy and the new theory," the topic which satisfies the community leaders' demand in the municipality of sub-district Kumphawapi.

5. About the preparation of the environment, the training room must be in good order with relaxing, moderate temperature and enough lights are provided.

Fig. 4 The training room of Udonthani Rajabhat University

6. The budget preparation is allocated with the goal to reduce costs and save expense in the best way as much as possible.

7. The design for the format of activities must focus on facilitating the training of senior adults.

8. The evaluation is divided into three phases: pre-training, in-training and post-training evaluations.

9. The trainees will receive the satisfaction questionnaires to respond according to their opinions.

The statistics used in data analysis rely on the statistical mean, percentage, standard deviation and statistical T-test.

Fig. 5 Registration

III. CONCLUSION

The conclusion of the research on transmitting the distance training to the community in the upper northeastern region can be summarized as follows :

1. The effectiveness of the distance training is shown in the Table I.

In-Training (E1)				
N	Full points	\bar{X}	S.D.	Percentage
30	30	24.47	2.92	81.56
Post-Training (E2)				
N	Full points	\bar{X}	S.D.	Percentage
30	30	16.07	2.15	80.33

From Table I, the findings indicate the average score in the in-training period standing at 81.56 percent and the average score in the post-training period at 80.33. Therefore, the E1/E2 equates 81.56/80.33 higher than the setup criterion assigned at 80/80.

Fig. 6 The training room of the municipality of sub-district Kumphawapi

2. The comparison of the achievements of the community leaders in the pre and post-training periods is shown in the Table II.

Training Room	Test	N	\bar{X}	S.D.	T
The municipality of sub-district Kumphawapi	Pre-training	30	12.03	2.63	14.33*
	Post-training	30	16.07	2.15	
Udonthani Rajabhat University	Pre-training	30	12.17	2.25	22.53*
	Post-training	30	16.13	2.19	

* The level of statistical significance is at .05

From Table II, the findings indicate that both the two groups of community leaders having the distance training in their separate locations have reached the average scores in the post-training period higher than those of the pre-training period with his level of statistical significance at .05.

3. The comparison of the achievements of the distance training from the two groups of community leaders can be presented in the Table III.

Training Room	N	\bar{X}	S.D.	T
The municipality of sub-district Kumphawapi	30	16.07	2.15	0.12
Udonthani Rajabhat University	30	16.13	2.19	

From Table III, the findings confirm the achievements in the distance training of the two groups in no different statistical terms.

Fig. 7 The training room of Udonthani Rajabhat University

Fig. 8 The training room of the municipality of sub-district Kumphawapi

4. The findings on the satisfaction associated with the distance training of both groups have been shown in the Table IV.

TABLE IV

SATISFACTION OF THE COMMUNITY LEADERS IN THE DISTANCE TRAINING				
No.	Item	\bar{X}	S.D	Ranking
1.	Interesting topics of the training	4.73	0.52	2
2.	Current and up-to-date topics of the training	4.80	0.55	1
3.	Ability of facilitators	4.33	0.88	9
4.	Levels of satisfaction in Q&A.	4.30	0.88	10
5.	Facilitators' politeness and friendliness	4.63	0.56	4
6.	Performance of assistant facilitators	4.23	0.90	12
7.	Performance of technicians	3.73	0.74	18
8.	Training documents	4.07	0.91	14
9.	Sharpness and brightness of monitor and broadcast signals	4.70	0.53	3
10.	Light condition in training room	4.20	0.85	13
11.	Suitability of training rooms	4.57	0.68	5
12.	Proper use of time in training	4.27	0.87	11
13.	Immediate helps in facilitators' explanations	4.03	0.89	15
14.	Participation in every activity	3.63	0.72	20
15.	Exchanges of learning experience within the group	4.53	0.73	6
16.	Ability to express as a result of group activity	3.80	0.85	17
17.	Satisfaction among the other participants in the training	3.93	0.91	16
18.	Increase in practical knowledge after the training	3.70	0.75	19
19.	The opportunity to apply what learned in the training in the day-to-day life situations	4.50	0.73	7
20.	The opportunity to transmit what learned to other members in the community	4.43	0.82	8
Total		4.26	0.76	-

From Table IV, the findings point to the high level of overall satisfaction. Going through each item, we see the 6 numbers getting the highest marks, they are : 1) the training is current and up-to-date for the present situation, 2) the interesting features of the training, 3) the sharpness and brightness of the monitor and broadcast signals, 4) the

facilitators' politeness and friendliness, 5) the suitability of training sites, 6) the exchanges within the group of participants. The other items also have received the high marks.

IV. DISCUSSION

This research discussion can be pointed out in four areas.

1. The efficiency of the distance training model as developed by the research assists the community leaders in the distance training to make the average scores of the respective training periods of E1 and E2 higher than the setup criterion. Therefore, it can be concluded that, in transmitting the distance training model to the community, it is necessary to carry out on every right step towards completion, the key to its efficiency.

2. The two groups of community leaders in the distance training have received higher scores in the post-training period than in the pre-training period. These scores indicate that they have gained more knowledge as a result of the application of the adult-learning theory in the distance training. The principle of adult learning is for those at the age of confidence and independent thinking. They are interested in learning things concerning their work and way of life. They like the friendly atmosphere without heavy-handed treatment [5]. Moreover, adults will decide for themselves as to what to learn and expect the immediate use of what they have learned [2].

3. The achievement in the training of the two groups are not different. Evidently, the distance training model as developed by the researcher can help far-distance community leaders learn as effectively as directly with the facilitators themselves.

4. From the evaluation of the community leaders' satisfaction, the findings show it in the highest level. Since the distance training model lays down the steps encompassing all aspects of training-determination of training courses, contents relevant to the trainees' needs, preparation of tools and equipment including suitable environment and training site arrangements. The evaluation of satisfaction of this training is consistent with Supatra Srisuwan's research, 2003 [6] which seeks to develop the two-way distance training consequently leading up to the trainees' high level of satisfaction.

REFERENCES

- [1] Buckley, R. & Caple, J. (2009). *The Theory and Practice of Training* (6th Ed). London. Kogan Page.
- [2] Cavalieri, S. (2007, July 20). *Adult Learning Theory Principles*. Adult Learning, 2(2), 18-21.
- [3] Oranuch Sukawesh. (2004). *Participants' evaluation on vocational training programs of Nonthaburi*. Thesis. Kasetsart University.
- [4] Office of the National Economic and Social Development Board. (2008). *human-centered development*. [Online]. Available : <http://www.nesdb.go.th/Default.aspx?tabid=139>. [2008, December 7].
- [5] Stephen, L. (1991). *Principles of adult learning* [Online]. Available : <http://honolulu.hawaii.edu/intranet/committees/FacDevCom/guidebk/teachtip/adults-2.htm>. [2007, November 1].
- [6] Supatra Srisuwan. (2002). *Development of Vocational Training of the duplex*. Doctoral Dissertation. Srinakharinwirot University.